

7 nutrient ingredients — Zn, Fe, Cu, Mn, Mg, B, Mo in chelated form) for 20 hours; and 18% with $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ in 200 ppm solution for 20 hours. Before planting, the treated seeds were sun-dried to their original moisture status. The increases in plant dry-matter accumulation ranged from 13 to 54%. Ash-free root weights also increased (13 to 63%); the increments over the control treatment were 63% with Na_2HPO_4 , 40% with NaH_2PO_4 , 40% with $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, and 37% with water soaking. The last treatment consisted of soaking seeds in distilled water for 24 or 48 hours and then drying to the original moisture status (“24 hours double” means that the 24-hour soaking was repeated). All seeds except those in the untreated control were treated with fungicide (Agrosan at 2 g/kg). Grain yields were 14 to 26% higher in crops raised from pretreated seeds (Table 1). The seeds were treated with NaCl (38 ppm for 6 hours), NaH_2PO_4 (156 ppm for 6 hours), and CoNO_3 (200 ppm for 20 hours) solutions and then dried to original moisture level. Close and significant relationships were found for grain yield and root-to-shoot ratio ($r = 0.86$), percentage of total available carbohydrate (TAC) in roots ($r = 0.90$), ash-free

Table 2. Water saturation deficit in leaves and ash-free root weight of rice varieties (V) at 30-45 cm depth, 50 days after sowing. West Benzal, India.

Seed treatment (T)	Water saturation deficit (%)			Decrease (%) from control	Ash-free root wt (mg/5 cm diam cylindrical core)			Increase (%) over control
	IET 2914	Dular	Mean		IET 2914	Dular	Mean	
	Control (untreated)	20.9	17.4		19.1		42	
Soaking in distilled water								
24 h	19.2	12.7	16.0	17	50	57	53	37
48 h	18.2	13.3	15.7	18	87	50	68	75
24 h double ^a	17.3	13.8	15.6	19	62	61	62	58
NaCl	17.0	13.7	15.5	19	37	48	42	9
NaH_2PO_4	15.6	15.5	15.6	19	75	47	61	56
Na_2HPO_4	14.8	12.8	13.8	28	86	60	73	86
$\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	15.9	14.5	15.2	21	52	71	61	57
CoNO_3	18.5	14.3	16.3	15	60	62	61	56
Agromin	16.3	13.3	14.8	23	68	50	59	51
Fungicide treated	18.0	16.5	17.3	10	62	31	46	19
Mean	15.5	14.3			63	52		
	V	T	V x T		V	T	V x T	
S Em (±)	1.0	0.7	1.2		7.4	8.1	11.5	
CD at 5%		2.0				23.0		

^aThe 24-h soaking was repeated.

deep-root weight ($r = 0.79$), and water saturation deficit in leaves ($r = -0.66$ for IET2914 and -0.74 for Dular). The relationships were also close and significant for shallow root (0–15 cm) weight and TAC content ($r = 0.79$); deep root (15–45 cm) weight and water saturation deficit ($r = -0.78$); and chlorophyll stability index and root weight ($r = -0.78$).

The increased vigor of the plants from pretreated seeds was due mainly to the better root growth, particularly of deep roots, which decreased the water saturation deficit (Table 2) and chlorophyll stability index values of leaves. The roots and shoots of plants from pretreated seeds also contained more TAC. ■

Time of fertilizer nitrogen application in rice culture

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The notoriously low utilization of fertilizer nitrogen by rice is thought to be largely caused by nitrogen losses in the soil-plant system. Of the various factors that affect nitrogen efficiency, the time of application is important. After transplanting, rice seedlings take a few days to recover (the “transplanting shock period”), and then start growing. Nitrogen applied during this period may be poorly utilized by the plants and much is probably lost to leaching, denitrification, and volatilization.

A field experiment was conducted during summer (Apr-Jun), 1978, to determine the best time of first nitrogen

Total nitrogen content (%)

Relationship between nitrogen content of the rice plant and days after transplanting. Ludhiana, India.

application to rice for higher yields. The soil — Fatehpur loamy sand — had a pH of 8.1 and was low in organic carbon. After transplanting, rice seedling samples were taken daily from selected treatments for 9 days and analyzed for total nitrogen content using the Technicon Nitrogen Autoanalyzer

following the 1966 technique of Warner and Jones.

The nitrogen content of rice plants tended to decrease during the first 4 days after transplanting (see figure). A gradual increase on the 5th and 6th days of sampling was followed by a sharp decline. The differential nitrogen

concentration of the rice plant with time may be explained by the plant's physiology during this period. In the first 4 days after transplanting, the roots were inactive. That might have limited the plant's water and nutrient absorption as reflected in the plants' withering, and yellowing, and their reduced nitrogen content. After 4 days, plant roots recovered from transplanting shock and regulated the water and nutrient supply. That condition was indicated by a return of greenness and increased nitrogen content in the plants. After 6 days, nitrogen was appropriated in the synthesis of metabolites and for fast plant growth. During this time the nitrogen supply probably was not commensurate with the rapid plant growth; thus the nitrogen content of the plants decreased sharply because of the "dilution effect."

To increase the efficiency of fertilizer use, it may be beneficial to apply nitrogen 5 days after transplanting. This

Effect of fungicide seed treatment on rice seedling growth

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The seedborne nature of sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn has been established. Seeds of ADT3 1 were collected from sheath blight-affected fields, treated with test fungicides, and stored in polythene bags for 3 days. The test fungicides thiophanate, captafol, fenaminosulf, triarimol, PCNB, carbendazim, captan, chloroneb, carboxin, benomyl, triphenyltin acetate, Agrosan, thiram, oxycarboxin, MEMC, chlorothalonil were used at 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2% levels. The treated seeds were tested for germination, seedling growth, and vigor. Some treated seeds were stored for 8 months and then tested for viability.

Benomyl, chlorothalonil, and carboxin increased seed germination considerably over the control. Oxycarboxin, carboxin, chlorothalonil, and benomyl significantly increased shoot growth. Carbendazim,

Comparison of basal and delayed application of first dose of nitrogen on two rice cultivars. Ludhiana, India.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)	
	Palman 579	PR106
T ₁	5.4	6.4
T ₂	5.7	6.6

^a T₁ = 40 kg N/ha at transplanting + 40 kg N 3 wk after transplanting (WT) + 40 kg N 6 WT. T₂ = 40 kg N/ha at 7 days after transplanting + 40 kg N 3 WT + 40 kg N 6 WT.

observation is supported by results of a replicated field experiment conducted on Fatehpur loamy sand in the 1978 kharif (Jul-Oct) (see table).

The data show that application of nitrogen at 7 days after transplanting gave 0.3 t/ha more yield than its application at transplanting. Therefore, fertilizer use efficiency may be higher if the first dose of nitrogen is applied 5–7 days after transplanting. But further large-scale field testing in different environments is needed. ■

triarimol, captafol, thiram, oxycarboxin, chlorothalonil, benomyl, and captan at 0.2%) increased the root growth of rice seedlings. Seedlings from the treated seeds were more vigorous than the control. Seeds treated with oxycarboxin and MEMC maintained more than 90% seed viability after 8 months of storage. ■

Azolla manuring for rice

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In earlier trials Srinivasan and Pari showed that azolla incorporation 1 week before planting at 10, 20, and 30 t/ha (nitrogen levels as high as 100 kg/ha) gave yields equal to 25, 50, and 75 kg N/ha, respectively. They also found that growing azolla until harvest but without incorporation gave no beneficial effects.

Because the field cannot be kept fallow for growing azolla after the kuruvai harvest, it was decided to grow azolla among the planted crop and incorporate it after it covered the surface. Three replicated trials were laid out

during 1978 thaladi with inoculum levels of 1, 2, and 3 t/ha at nitrogen levels of 0 to 100 kg/ha in slabs of 25 kg. P₂O₅ and K₂O were uniformly applied at 50 kg/ha before planting. The test variety was IR20. Azolla was sown 1 week after planting; the water level was maintained at 5 cm. The inoculum levels at 1, 2, and 3 t/ha covered the field 55, 33, and 15 days after application, respectively. Azolla was incorporated after the water was drained.

In the trial where azolla inoculum was applied at 3 t/ha, a yield increase equal

Effect of azolla manuring on grain yield of rice. Aduthurai, India.

N levels (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha) at azolla inoculum level of		
	1 t/ha	2 t/ha	3 t/ha
0	2.9	2.8	2.9
0 + azolla	3.0	3.1	3.4
25	3.5	3.3	3.2
25 + azolla	3.5	3.5	3.6
50	3.6	3.5	3.1
50 + azolla	3.8	3.8	4.0
75	4.0	3.9	4.2
75 + azolla	4.1	4.0	4.6
100	4.4	4.3	4.7
100 + azolla	4.4	4.5	5.2
CD (P = 0.05%)	0.4	0.5	0.3

to that of 25 kg N/ha was observed (see table). In trials with inoculum levels of 1 and 2 t/ha there was no appreciable yield increase because of the delayed incorporation of azolla (62 and 40 days after planting, respectively). ■

Soil loss due to roguing in rice seed production plots

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The roguing of offtypes is a standard practice in pure seed production programs. The major roguing operation takes place after flowering. Uprooting the entire plant speeds the removal of rogues, but a considerable amount of topsoil sticking to the roots is also removed from the plot in the process.

We randomly sampled rogues uprooted from our rice seed-production plots,